

The MASTER CODE and the BINARY CODE of the UNIVERSAL GENETIC CODE

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ABSTRACT :

We demonstrate here the existence of « The MASTER CODE of Biology », a hyper code UNIFYING GENOMICS (DNA double strand) and PROTEOMICS (coresponding amino acids) for an hypothetic gene constituying the 64 codons of the genetic code sequence.

Then we show also the roots of a Fractal « BINARY CODE » characterizing the texture of the PROTEOMICS pattern generalized for all sequence : coding, junk DNA, whole chromosomes and genomes.

The Genetic Code Table sequence is :

VCGJCP

TTTTTCTTATTGCTTCTCCTACTGATTATCATAATGGTTGTCGTAGTGTCTTCCTCATCGCC
TCCCCACCGACTACCACAACGGCTGCCGCAGCGTATTACTAATAGCATCACCAACAGA
ATAACAAAAAGGATGACGAAGAGTGTTGCTGATGGCGTCGCCGACGGAGTAGCAGAAG
GGGTGGCGGAGGG

METHODS :

The Universal Genetic Code MAP

		Second letter							
		U	C	A	G				
U	UUU	Phe	UCU	Ser	UAU	Tyr	UGU	Cys	U
	UUC		UCC		UAC		UGC		C
	UUA	Leu	UCA	UGA	UAA	Stop	UGA	Stop	A
	UUG		UCG		UAG		UGG		G
C	CUU	Leu	CCU	Pro	CAU	His	CGU	Arg	U
	CUC		CCC		CAC		CGC		C
	CUA	Gln	CCA	CAG	CAA	Gln	CGA	Arg	A
	CUG		CCG		CGG		G		
A	AUU	Ile	ACU	Thr	AAU	Asn	AGU	Ser	U
	AUC		ACC		AAC		AGC		C
	AUA	Met	ACA	AAG	AAA	Lys	AGA	Arg	A
	AUG		ACG		AGG		G		
G	GUU	Val	GCU	Ala	GAU	Asp	GGU	Gly	U
	GUC		GCC		GAC		GGC		C
	GUA	Glu	GCA	GAG	GAA	Glu	GGA	Gly	A
	GUG		GCG		GAG		GGG		G

The MASTER CODE of BIOLOGY

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Six Fractal Codes of Biological Life Unifying ATOMS, WAVES and INFORMATION: Perspectives in Exobiology, Cancers Basic Research and Artificial Intelligence Biomimetism Decisions Making

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Abstract

In this theoretical discovery of a law of Life, there is MATHEMATICS (Geometry, Bits and Numbers) that UNIFY 3 universes as complementary as ATOMIC MASS, WAVES, and INFORMATION (DNA, RNA and Amino Acids). The discovery of a simple numerical formula for the projection of all the atomic mass of life-sustaining CONHSP bioatoms leads to the

emergence of a set of Nested CODES unifying all the biological, genetic and genomic components by unifying them from bioatoms up to 'to whole genomes. In particular, we demonstrate the existence of a digital meta-code common to the three languages of biology that are RNA, DNA and amino acid sequences. Through this meta-code, genomic and proteomic images appear almost analogous and correlated. The analysis of the textures of these images then reveals a binary code as well as an undulatory code whose analysis on the human genome makes it possible to predict the alternating bands constituting the cariotypes of the chromosomes. The application of these codes to perspectives in astrobiology, cancer, and specifically in INFORMATION THEORY with the emergence of binary codes and regions of local stability (voting process), whose fractal nature we demonstrate, is illustrated.

PREFACE by Professor Luc Montagnier

After the discovery of the DNA double helix structure allowing both the stable storage of genetic information and its transfer through messenger RNA to protein synthesis organelles themselves structured by RNA most abundant in cells, the ribosomal.

This wonder of nature exists in ALL living beings from the virus to humans and is based on two codes, the linear sequence of nucleotides and that derived from codons where three nucleotides allow with a certain flexibility - synonymous codons - the choice in the twenty amino acids.

But we are missing a third CODE the one governing at multicellular beings from the rotifer to human, the stabilized modulation of gene expression in a nutshell the differentiation of cells from the single cell of the fertilized egg.

It is logical to think that this program which begins as soon as fertilization is written in the DNA. We are also prone to associate it with non-coding DNA sequences although they control gene expression.

I introduce here the notion developed by Jean-Claude Pérez of mathematical harmony, a higher order present in all living beings and whose existence it finds in genomes, including those of viruses.

Thus the natural evolution of variants of the genome of coronavirus Covid 19 tends towards increasingly long Fibonacci series.

It remains to determine the Who, the How and the Why of such developments.

I will bet with my mathematician colleague that waves and fractals play a role.

Luc Montagnier

Addendum by Robert Friedman M.D

Jean-claude has given scientists a strong new direction for research. He has identified a unified field of science guided by the Golden Ratio and Fibonacci Sequence. By identifying an overall guiding principle that makes possible fractal-like nesting at all levels of biological manifestation, future researchers can begin with the "whole" instead of the "parts". If we know that complex systems are organized at varying levels by the Golden Ratio and Fibonacci Sequence, we can look for those universal patterns first and then fill in the gaps with small details to complete the picture. It's like having an overall view of a crossword puzzle before beginning to assemble the individual pieces. Without an overarching vision and guiding principle, completing the puzzle is infinitely more difficult. Once scientists and researchers realize and begin using this "SECRET IN HIDDEN IN PLAIN SIGHT," their discoveries will be orders of magnitude more fruitful.

Robert Friedman M.D

RESULTS :

APL session :

CG 64 CODONS

VCGJCP

GENETIC CODE MASTER CODE PROOF GENCHROMPARALLEL2 VCGJCP

VCGJCP

TTTTTCTTATTGCTTCTCCTACTGATTATCATAATGGTTGTCGTAGTGTCTTCCTCATCGCCTCCCCACCGAC
TACCACAACGGCTGCCGACGCGTATTACTAATAGCATCACCAACAGAATAACAAAAAGGATGACGAAGAGT
GTTGCTGATGGCGTCGCCGACGGAGTAGCAGAAGGGGTGGCGGAGGG

'GENETIC CODE MASTER CODE PROOF ' GENCHROMPARALLEL2 VCGJCP

RESULTS IN INTDNA AND INTPRO1 AND INTPRO2

===== Strand1 =====
ANALYSING GLOBAL GENOMICS/PROTEOMICS COUPLING RATIO PERCENTAGE...
_____ UNIVERSALIS GENETIC CODE (Global Unified Genetic Code) _____

GENOMICS/PROTEOMICS Global Coupling percentage: 80.49908

===== Strand2 =====
ANALYSING GLOBAL GENOMICS/PROTEOMICS COUPLING RATIO PERCENTAGE...
_____ UNIVERSALIS GENETIC CODE (Global Unified Genetic Code) _____

GENOMICS/PROTEOMICS Global Coupling percentage: 85.08242

==== Strand 1 =====
MAJOR GENOMICS SITES...
15 FIRST + Major sites: 1 33 2 32 34 64 3 31 35 63 4 30 36 62 5
15 LAST - minor sites: 52 50 48 46 20 18 16 14 53 51 49 47 45 21 19
MAJOR PROTEOMICS SITES...

15 FIRST + Major sites: 29 30 31 28 32 26 1 33 27 25 64 34 24 2 63
15 LAST - Minor sites: 45 46 49 17 48 16 47 15 50 18 57 14 56 13 55

==== Strand 2 =====

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MAJOR GENOMICS SITES...

15 FIRST + Major sites: 1 33 2 32 34 64 3 31 35 63 4 30 36 62 5
15 LAST - Minorsites: 52 50 48 46 20 18 16 14 53 51 49 47 45 21 19

MAJOR PROTEOMICS SITES...

15 FIRST Major sites: 1 32 33 31 64 61 62 63 37 30 34 35 2 36 3
15 LAST Minor sites: 17 16 49 18 48 51 50 14 13 12 19 15 21 20 22

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===== VECTPIM1....

GENOMICS teeth of saw PERCENT CODE...

INCREASE /\ DECREASE: 0.5 0.5

PROTEOMICS teeth of saw PERCENT CODE...

INCREASE /\ DECREASE: 0.59375 0.40625

CODONS 1 TO 64

RANGE NUCLEO: 1 189

=====
===== VECTPIM2...

GENOMICS teeth of saw PERCENT CODE...

INCREASE /\ DECREASE: 0.5 0.5

PROTEOMICS teeth of saw PERCENT CODE...

INCREASE /\ DECREASE: 0.59375 0.40625

CODONS 1 TO 64

RANGE NUCLEO: 1 189

SURFACE41C LIBELLUS

SURFACE42C LIBELLUS

SURFACE41C LIBELLUS

ANALYSING GLOBAL GENOMICS/PROTEOMICS COUPLING RATIO PERCENTAGE...

_____ UNIVERSALIS GENETIC CODE (Global Unified Genetic Code) _____

GENOMICS/PROTEOMICS Global Coupling percentage: 80.49908

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Figure 1 – Master Code of the Universal Genetic Code sequence (double stranded DNA)

Figure 2 – Master Code of the Universal Genetic Code sequence (Antisens double stranded DNA)

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION:

THE “M” FORM OF THE MASTER CODE FROM THE GENETIC CODE TABLE:

On the form of this double image of genomics/proteomics coupling:

Remember that the Master Code curves produce a ranking of the relative influences throughout the sequence for each of the codon/anticodon pairs (Genomics) or for their corresponding pairs of amino acids (Proteomics).

As a result, the most influential sites will be those located towards the bottom (these are in fact those which have a CG predominance). Reciprocally, those who are located towards the top of the images have a weak influence and are rather those who are rich in TA.

We then understand why the first and third quarters of the images are ascending while the second and fourth quarters are descending.

In fact, the genetic code table was explored by column to form the analyzed gene, therefore following the columns T, then C then A then G, these letters being the SECOND base (see £) of each of the codons, therefore the most influential. Which explains this “M” shape of the images.

(£) The fact that it is the second base of the codons (columns of the genetic code table) which structures this Master code in "M" reminds us of the importance of this position in the structure of genes

(Chiusano et al,2000). Indeed, these authors associate the second position T or A with alpha helix type structures, and the second position C or G with beta structures.

What a strange link with our observations about the "W" Master code signatures of all Prions (Perez, Montagnier & Moret Chalmin, 2023). In these W signatures, the Prion type regions are the "descendant" regions of Master Code, therefore the regions where the second base of the codons is predominantly C or G. These 2 observations reinforce each other.

THE PROTEOMICS MODULATION BINARY CODE:

Already in these 2 curves we would detect the trace of the binary modulation of the Proteomics images:

In the results, what do these values mean?

===== VECTPIM1....

GENOMICS teeth of saw PERCENT CODE...

INCREASE /\.DECREASE:

0.5 0.5

PROTEOMICS teeth of saw PERCENT CODE...

INCREASE /\.DECREASE:

0.59375 0.40625

Figure 3 - Fractal « sawtooth like » texture of Proteomics Master code ^ pattern (blue).

In the figure above, we see that the fractal textures or roughness are a kind of predominantly increasing sawtooth.

Also in the result above for the genetic code table, if we look for some kind of first order mathematical derivative for each position, we thus measure this type of increase/decrease textures.

We see a perfect equality of 50/50% for Genomics, but an imbalance close to 60/40% for Proteomics.

In fact if for any sequence, including junk DNA, the Genomics/Proteomics correlation is always strong, see figures below representing MASTER CODE signatures in the cases of :

- The coding gene, the HUMAN PRION, 96.8% correlating Genomics/Proteomics (Figure 4).
- The whole 1 megabases MALARIA chromosome2, 98.8% correlating Genomics/Proteomics (Figure 5).
- The 100kb 17q22 HUMAN chromosome17 region, 99.93% correlating Genomics/Proteomics (Figure 6).

Figure 4 - The coding gene, the HUMAN PRION, 96.8% correlating Genomics/Proteomics

Figure 6 illustration of the high correlation coupling between genomics and proteomics

Figure 5 - The whole 1 megabases MALARIA chromosome2, 98.8% correlating Genomics/Proteomics

Figure 6 - The 100kb 17q22 HUMAN chromosome17 region, 99.93% correlating Genomics/Proteomics

On the contrary, the increase/decrease sawtooth textures are radically different in the two cases of Genomics and Proteomics Master Code signatures:

As the images below illustrate,

Figure 7 - Evidence of the about 60% Genomics texture (brown) and binary 30% / 60% Proteomics texture (blue) in the case of a 33 Mega-bases region in Human chromosome 22.

Figure 8 - Distribution of the about 60% Genomics one attractor texture (brown) and binary 30% / 60% Proteomics two attractors texture (blue) in the case of the same 33 Mega-bases region in Human chromosome 22 analysed in Figure7.

GENOMES BINARY CODE: proof of BIOBITS around 2 attractors: HUMAN CHROMOSOME 4

Figure 9 - Evidence of two Attractors : the Beautiful proof of the Proteomics Binary Code fractal texture structuring and modulating the whole Human Chromosome 4.

Genomics textures appear Gaussian distributed around 60%.

On the contrary, and **"this is a major discovery"**, Proteomics textures are "modulated" according to a sort of BINARY CODE 0/1, i.e. here approximately 30% / 60% (but these percentages correspond more exactly to phi and phi/2 or $\phi = 0.618 = 1/\Phi$ ($\Phi=1.618$ the Golden Ratio)).

We show in these 2 figures 10 and 11 below how this binary code modulates the entire human genome...

Figure 10 - Proof of Genomics Master code single texture (blue) and Proteomics Master code BINARY CODE (red) overlapping and modulating whole Human chromosomes 1 to 8.

Human Genome Chr 9 to Y BINARY LOGIC CODE Proteomics modulation

Figure 16 The 16 other remaining Chromosomes (1 to 8) of the whole HUMAN GENOME

Figure 11 - Proof of Genomics Master code single texture (blue) and Proteomics Master code BINARY CODE (red) overlapping and modulating whole Human chromosomes 9 to Y.

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